

EMPOWER, ELEVATE AND EXCEL THROUGH MORALITY AND SPIRITUALITY

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Abstract:

Science and technology aims at the wellbeing of mankind. It makes various efforts for bringing happiness in human life. Almost all the discoveries and inventions aims at making life more comfortable and leading towards the material, economic progress. Within last few decades' science and technology has progressed with a faster pace. Modern man was surprised at the wonders of scientific progress. There was a time when it was thought that science can control any situation immediately, however since the onset of covid-19 pandemic surprised mankind and many of them realized that with the advancement of science, technology and especially medical science there still remains some mysteries of nature which are difficult to control. Covid-19 Pandemic has shown that life is unpredictable. On the one hand science and technology aims at making life more comfortable and on the other hand it has made such weapons and drugs which leads to the destruction, miseries. With the new development of science and technology, new problems arise. The world has shrink today, turning it into global village but aloofness, alienation, mental problems, frustration, depression are also increasing. When a person is suffering from these problems he/she cannot think of excelling oneself. Peace of mind, clarity of thought, stability in life and inner strength helps a person to empower oneself. Empowered person can not only elevate himself or herself but also can make an attempt to excel in the field chosen by him/her.

The present paper attempts to review the different ways of solving the problems of man and the ways in which he/she can empower oneself. In this journey of empowerment what role does morality and spirituality plays is also discussed in this paper.

Key Words: *empowerment, excel, morality, spirituality*

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I. Introduction

The information technology has transformed world into global village, however instead of creating a global family it has resulted into creating a global exploitation market. This is the result of man's moral weaknesses, selfishness and greed for power, for money etc. Neither science nor technologies have any control over these impulses and passions. Empowered person is one who can assess oneself as well as the situation and is able to take the appropriate decisions. The World Bank defines "empowerment as the process of enhancing the capacity of individuals or groups and to transform those choices into desired actions and outcomes." Many problems of modern man arises as he or she is not able to realize the potentiality or various capacities an individual possess. Once a person realizes his/her potentiality then he/she make efforts to utilize it and to elevate oneself by making right choices and bringing them into action thereby excelling oneself. In this process role of morality and spirituality is very important. It is through inculcating moral values, practicing moral values and spiritual values many problems can be resolved and thereby empowers a person elevating one's position and bringing flourishing in his life. Socrates once said an unexamined life is not worth living. Covid -19 pandemic have taught us many things in life. People's working style changed, most of them spent their time at home and realized the importance of relationships, values and simplicity. It's time to evaluate and examine the problems of modern man and also to find out the ways of reducing it.

II. Problems of modern man

Covid-19 pandemic situation has increased the problems of modern man. Bereavement, isolation fear, anxiety, uncertainties of life, the rise in unemployment, fear of losing jobs, loss of income are some of the examples of problems which presently many of them are facing. Domestic violence, drug abuse, alcohol addiction, insomnia is also on rise. During lock down when all the social activities stopped and people started spending more time on social media and in the virtual world the family relationships got affected. The number of divorce cases have shoot up. The pandemic induced poverty has affected the gender poverty gap. In the words of D.K. Chakravorty "The real tragedy of the present era is that it has forgotten that the problem of humanity is fundamentally one of spirituality. A free and peaceful society will emerge only when spirituality irrigates man's personal and social life."¹

¹ D K. Chakravorty –Relevance of Ancient Indian Values from Spirituality, Science and Technology. –page 96

The pace of the change prior to Covid-19 pandemic was at a very faster rate, which became a source of anguish, if we want that societies to be harmonious, then there must be more peaceful and caring relationship among human beings. During the lockdown period many of them volunteered and came forward for helping the needy people. Pandemic created opportunities for the transformation in the way in which humanitarian aid is delivered.

If in any society instant gratification is the norm, then the people of that society faces many problems. People want instant results for their work, instant solutions for the problems. People are not ready to wait, in the present moment as they are worried about the transitory nature of all things, younger generation is impatient, they want gratification of all kinds without any delay. With the changing scenario of the present society more patience is required in the new normal.

Present society emphasis individual freedom. It believes that freedom is essential for the progress of society. Freedom without conscience is dangerous. Freedom has to be used in a rational way, otherwise it is dangerous to society, and freedom comes with responsibility. Pandemic has taught us that by following the rules of restriction and various curbs are required for our own health and safety. Moral thinking and spiritual beliefs leads to a responsible behavior, it helps in establishing a proper link between freedom and responsibility.

Problems like crime and violence arises when people do not give importance to the human dignity. In the present society human dignity is correlated to economic wellbeing and productive capacity of a person. At times some poor people may feel humiliated. Humiliation breeds violence and social disintegration. Harmonious and peaceful society requires that people should respect each other. Strong moral principles and rules of conduct are required to solve the contemporary problems like increasing corruption, inefficiency and lack of effectiveness of public services. There is vast disparity and feeling of separateness between those who deliver the services and those who are supposed to be beneficiaries. Those who are providing services expect something extra for those services, which they are supposed to do, or which is their duty. it is only through the practice of moral values person will become aware of his duties and then he will be committed and loyal to the organization for which he is working.

III. Morality

Human beings have made many attempts to know the ultimate reality; the search for truth

is an important task. Various Philosophers, religious leaders, scientists are making various attempts to understand the truth. The pursuit of truth is based on the path of morality. Morality is the basis of all types of knowledge .it is also the basis of all good and noble aspects of life. Lack of morality resulted into various problems which mankind is facing today. As Dr Paul Brunton writes “The real tragedy of our time lies not so much in the unprecedented external events themselves as in the unprecedented ethical destitution and spiritual affirmity which they glaringly reveal.”²

Morality refers to social aspect of an individual person. It has social relevance. Man’s conduct, behaviour is influenced by the society in which he is living. Similarly, his behaviour, conduct influences other people. He lives with others in a society. Dr Rajendra Prasad says “A distinguishing or necessary feature of being moral is to care and be concerned with the welfare of others, to have a respect for the dignity of each and every person.”³

A responsible and rational moral individual understands the value of others and therefore he gives respect to others and also to oneself. He recognizes the importance of human dignity. “Human dignity can be defined as the fundamental goodness inherent in every human being; the very nature of the human being as created by God; the central and the inevitable core of the person; an inalienable right given to all by the mere fact of existing; the source of life itself.; the origin of self-respect and respect for others; and the very essence of the relationship between the being, nature and divine.”⁴ “Ethics is a branch of philosophy; it is moral philosophy or philosophical thinking about morality, moral problems and moral judgments.”⁵ This view explains that Ethics is concerned with morality and its problems. Morality has a social aspect as well as personal aspect. To its social aspect Frankenna calls ‘social enterprises’. He further says “it is also largely social in its origin, sanctions, and functions. As first encountered by the individual at any rate, it is an instrument of society as a whole, for the guidance of individuals and smaller groups.”⁶

IV. For solving the problems of modern man both morality and spirituality is very useful. Spiritual search for knowledge results in goodness, compassion, love for

² Dr Paul Brunton- Spiritual crisis of a man . page 8

³ Rajendra Prasad - On Historiography of classical Indian Ethics page 4

⁴ A Report of the Seminar- Ethical and spiritual dimension of social progress: world summit for social development held in Bled, Slovenia, 28-30 oct 1994 There is no mention of author –pub by United Nations 1995

⁵ William Frankenna, Ethics page no 4

⁶ Ibid page no 6

humanity, control over selfish impulses and passions. This human goodness has the power to move societies in positive directions. Lack of goodness results in fear, despair, selfishness, arrogance and the will to dominate others.

Spirituality encourages values of compassion and a sense of belongingness. It recognizes common humanity beyond differences in culture and religion. Vedic statement ‘Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam’ is the best example of social harmony and belongingness. Whole world is treated as one family. “A calm and joyful celebration of human diversity, which is completely different from reticent and grudging acceptance of the relativism of opinions and customs, requires a spiritual foundation and shared values. In order to become open to such a celebration of diversity, the dominant culture must become open to such a celebration of diversity, the dominant culture must become less predatory, less impatient and more spiritual.”⁷

Spirituality is knowing our true real nature, and thereby attaining peace. Spirituality means to live a life with full awareness it is an inner development, knowing one’s true nature. Vedantins says Sachchidananda i.e. Existence, Knowledge and Bliss is our real nature. But due to ignorance we do not know our real nature. We identify ourselves with body, or places or with mental conditions, spirituality consist in knowing the real nature of man.

What man wants in his life is happiness and satisfaction in life. The greatest satisfaction from life, inner peace and calm and confusion free mind and tension free life is what man aspires for.

In the search for self-knowledge man attempts to understand oneself. If he succeeds in understanding oneself completely he will experience greatest satisfaction (Saints life). Self-realisation is highest purpose of life. According to S Radhakrishnan, “The Hindu Dharma says, man does not live by bread alone, nor by his work, capital, ambition or power or relations to external nature. He lives or must live by his life of spirit. Moksa is self –emancipation, the fulfillment of the spirit in us in the heart of the eternal. This is what gives ultimate satisfaction and all other activities are directed to the realisation of this end.”⁸ Dr Paul Brunton says “for too long most people thought that search for higher

⁷ Ibid-page33

⁸ S. Radhakrishnan – The Hindu View of Life page-81

purpose in life was not so important as the several lower purposes; it did not even matter. They needed to be shocked into awareness that nothing else can take its place.”⁹

In the spiritual path discriminative power of intellect and control of the mind is very important. The seeker should cultivate an intelligent control over the senses and mind. Kathopnishad describes that the person who lacks knowledge of discrimination and whose mind is not under control, has his/her sense organs beyond his/her control just like the vicious horse of a charioteer. One who is thus not constantly bringing his/her discriminative understanding in curbing the impulses of mind is one who is unyoked. If mind is occupied with worldly desires, then it will be difficult to concentrate mind on the spiritual practice, so mind should be empty from worldly desires, and the only prominent desire should be of ‘Self-realization’, as if this desire is not there then there won’t be any efforts.. This path is not for weak- minded but only those who are confident about themselves and have a strong mind, and courage can travel this path. As mentioned in Kathopnishad- walking on this path is walking like a edge of a razor. A person has to put all his efforts on this path. and it is not easily attainable. The path of self-realization is not so easy, while achieving the goals a person may come across various temptations He requires strong moral character so that he will not be tempted by worldly attractions. So spirituality is not possible without being moral.

Spirituality will definitely help a person to be more moral and more useful to the society becoming more responsible members of a society. This will help in realizing one’s potentiality fully, and through this one can not only be empowered but also can be elevated and will excel in the journey of life.

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⁹ Dr Paul Brunton *Spiritual Crisis of Man* page 61